

**ADAPTING TO THE MATATAG CURRICULUM'S NEW SUBJECT TIME
ALLOCATION: THE ROLE OF LAC SESSIONS FOR GRADE 4
TEACHERS IN GES**

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Adapting to the MATATAG Curriculum's New Subject Time Allocation: The Role of LAC Sessions for Grade 4 Teachers in GES

Ruth C. Colon*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Learning Action Cell (LAC) is an important part of a teacher's adaptation to new time allocations in the educational curricula, such as the MATATAG Curriculum. In LAC sessions, discussion of time allocation goals will ensure consistency in implementation but with quality instruction and engagement of students through effective classroom management. This study aims to identify how the Grade 4 Teachers of Gabi Elementary School (GES) can adjust to and cope with the MATATAG Curriculum's new subject time allocation. The study used both mixed-method research designs which allows for a richer exploration of the challenges and strategies involved in curriculum adaptation. This survey will employ a Likert Scale to measure teachers' responses. The sample population consists of four Grade 4 teachers. The result implies that in order to adapt and cope with the MATATAG Curriculum New Subject Time Allocation the teachers should; 1. teacher preparedness, 2. challenges identified by teachers, and 3. the effectiveness of Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions. The result of the study would be a great help to the administration of Gabi Elementary School (GES) to consider using new teaching strategies that will encourage and motivate teachers to learn, relearn and to learn again.

Keywords: *time allocation, MATATAG Curriculum, adapting and coping, teaching strategies*

Introduction

The Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the MATATAG Curriculum to allay some apprehensions over purported shortcomings in the K–12 program, which raised questions regarding the efficacy of the Philippine educational system (Estrellado, 2023). The MATATAG Curriculum, also known as "Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa," aims to simplify the current curriculum in order to prioritize learners' mastery of reading and numeracy skills while focusing on key subjects.

"The MATATAG Curriculum marks a vital shift in the educational landscape of the Philippines, as it aims to enhance the quality of education through a more standardized and competency-based approach" (Kilag, 2024). Many believe that this lack of knowledge is due to not enough hours spent on professional development. As a result, there has been a steady increase in the number of professional development opportunities available to teachers in various teaching areas over the past few years (e.g., Fishman, Best, Marx, & Tal, 2001b). However, even though there are more professional development opportunities for teachers now, we still do not have a clear understanding of what makes professional development effective, what teachers actually learn from it, or how it affects student outcomes (Fishman, Best, Marx & Tal, 2001a; Wilson & Berne, 1999). Different issues such as overloaded of curriculum, excessive teaching demands, and an overwhelming academic load have hindered the mastery of fundamental skills like reading and mathematics (Tarraya, 2023). Consequently, there has been a growing demand for curriculum reforms that prioritizes the development of core competencies and addresses the diverse needs of learners (De Guzman, 2003). As the new curriculum is set to be implemented for Grade 4 in the 2024-2025 school year, teachers face different challenges of adapting their teaching methods such as to meet the revised subject time allocations and learning objectives. Curriculum adaptation oftentimes poses various problems for the teachers, hence affecting their well-being and job satisfaction. Overloaded workload, time or training needed for carrying out changes that require more preparation and enhanced teaching approach for effective implementation are some of the common stressors. In the case of MATATAG Curriculum, it has been problematic for the teachers to adjust their instructional strategies because of the time allocations provided. It is due to the drastic shifts wherein everything in teaching practice needs to be modified (Westwood, 2018).

Research Objectives

The main goal of this research is to examine how Grade 4 educators are able to adjust and manage the recently introduced changes in subject time allocations under the MATATAG Curriculum by utilizing Learning Action Cell (LAC) meetings effectively. This study delves into the methods utilized in LAC sessions that improve teachers' capacity to modify their instructional plans and teaching approaches in line, with the updated curriculum guidelines.

1. To evaluate the Grade 4 teachers' readiness to adapt to MATATAG Curriculum changes in instructional strategies and time usage.
2. To investigate the challenges faced by Grade 4 teachers in adapting to the new curriculum, their impact on their teaching practices, and the impact on student outcomes.
3. To explore the different tactics employed during LAC sessions to enable teachers to adjust in lesson plans and teaching styles based on new curriculum changes.
4. To evaluate how effective the LAC sessions were in terms of pupil learning and engagement on the changes that occurred in the provision of subject time.

Literature Review

This literature review focuses on time allocation, coping strategies, and teaching methods as factors influencing the adaptation of teachers towards the MATATAG Curriculum. All these elements shape the success of curriculum implementation and support the professional growth of the teacher.

The MATATAG Curriculum

The MATATAG (Makatao at Makabansa, Tapat, At Tagumpay) Curriculum in the Philippines is to "have character building, foundational skills, and contextualized learning" to which the Department of Education continues to remark (Department of Education, 2023). Thus, learning competency relevance and adaptability towards societal needs will be increased when the required competencies are focused on. Change is, however, difficult for a teacher, especially when there are changes in content areas or instructional methods. Time adjustment, time management, and maintaining conformity with new curricula tend to be issues raised frequently by teachers in discussions over instructional change (Orencia & Villena, 2021). Most analyses of curriculum change tend to point out the key characteristics of successful implementation. There is a clear connection that must be drawn here-between communication, adequate means for resources, and opportunities for professional development on one's handling changes in expectations or adjustments made in teaching practice-Darling-Hammond et al., 2017.

Time Allocation in Curriculum Implementation

Time is critical in curriculum development and enactment regarding pacing teacher content delivery and teacher effectiveness. Findings on effective time use during curricula influence teacher performance and student outcome. New curricula introduce time allocation changes, which can mean new teaching schedules and expectations where the workload and instructional flow of teachers may be challenged (Blömeke et al., 2015). The best time usage will always be that which tries to balance content coverage in order to have opportunities that will lead to deeper learning and student engagement. Studies show that the instructional time in blocks for various subject areas should balance complexity and the goals of learning for that particular subject area, thus, if the blocks are too rigid or insufficient, then it may lead to rushing the instruction or failing to have the students comprehend what has been taught (Ehren et al., 2013).

Adapting and Coping with Curriculum Changes

Teachers have to change their instructional practices, assessment techniques, and time-management skills while adapting curriculum reforms. The coping effort comes not just individually but in collaboration, as teachers have to merge new curriculum demands into established routines (Day & Gu, 2010). Support mechanisms, in this case, professional learning communities and more structured session, such as Learning Action Cells (LAC), offer opportunities for problem-solving collectively and shared learning (Vangrieken et al., 2017). Effective coping strategies for the adaptation of curricula will include continuous training, mentorship, and feedback mechanisms that allow perfecting their practices and realign them to curricular goals. Moreover, resilience and adaptability are the qualities required for teachers to better handle the stressors for any curriculum change (Kyriacou, 2001).

Teaching Strategies for Effective Adaptation

Teaching strategies are very important to ensure that instructors cope with the change in curriculum reforms without compromising instructional effectiveness. There is evidence that flexible, student-centered strategies like differentiated instruction, project-based learning, and formative assessment are useful in changing new curriculum structures (Tomlinson, 2014). For example, differentiated instruction enables the teacher to vary their strategy according to different needs among students. This is highly useful where curriculum change influences the mode of content delivery and time (Subban, 2006). In addition, formative assessments provide continuous feedback upon which teachers can alter their pacing and instructional focus to be responsive to the speed at which the student is progressing. Teachers are also driven toward reflective practice whereby they review and reflect on their own teaching practices, on how they can continuously improve toward the goals of a curriculum (Schon, 1983). Further, the studies show that professional development is a source of adaptive strategies that can make teachers capable in efforts to cope with curriculum reforms and maintain quality instruction (Borko, 2004).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods research design to gain a comprehensive understanding on how the Grade 4 teachers adapt and cope with the MATATAG Curriculum through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. The researcher was able to conduct a thorough investigation of the difficulties and tactics associated with curriculum modification by combining quantitative and qualitative methods.

The integration of both quantitative and qualitative approaches will enable in-depth exploration of teacher experiences since it captures the general trends and perceptions in addition to the specific challenges teachers encounter while implementing curriculum. The data from surveys provide measurable insights into the overall satisfaction of teachers with the new curriculum, their perception of the effectiveness of the new curriculum, and the level of support received through LAC sessions. This data draws out larger patterns, such

as how adaptation differs with the years of experience or even which subjects' teachers are teaching. Meanwhile, qualitative data obtained from interviews will give a deeper and more personalized view of how these strategies can differ uniquely between teachers and what practical, emotional, and collaborative roles LAC sessions play in making adaptations happen.

Against this backdrop, the integration of these approaches will help provide a rich understanding of how structured support during LAC sessions supports teacher resilience, adaptability, and professional growth within the context of curriculum reform.

Participants

The selected population for this study will be the four (4) Grade 4 teachers of Gabi Elementary School, a selected school that implements the MATATAG Curriculum. A purposive sampling method will thus be applied to ascertain that the research will include teachers who are actually making an active participation in LAC sessions and curriculum change. Since they are the main target subjects in ascertaining the implementation of the changes in the curriculum at this level, the study only involves teaching subjects of Grade 4 teachers only. For there were only four Grade 4 teachers at Gabi Elementary School, all of them were selected to give detailed analysis relevant to that grade. The number of teachers in the sample will determine sample size and achieve broadness in terms of variety in teaching philosophies and the experiences they have had.

Instrument

The respondents were given a questionnaire that the researchers developed, which is made up of the four teachers. Multiple-choice and Likert scale questions regarding the MATATAG Curriculum implementation were used to measure satisfaction. This questionnaire was designed to gather information on various topics, including demographic information and a rating scale assessing the perceived effectiveness of the new time allocation, challenges faced, and support received from LAC Sessions.

The statistical analysis of survey data will help identify the patterns and relations. Thematic analysis will be used on qualitative data extracted from interviews to identify recurrent themes and understanding about the experiences and strategies of teachers. Triangulation of data will be supported through observational checklists and provide a comprehensive evaluation of LAC sessions' effectiveness.

Future research should look at the longitudinal study of the MATATAG Curriculum: the adaptation over time, the effect of the LAC sessions on teaching, and student outcomes in the relation to teachers' adaptation for a comprehensive understanding.

Procedure

In-depth Interviews: Each of the four teachers will participate in semi-structured interviews to discuss their experiences, challenges, and coping strategies related to the new time allocation. These interviews will explore how LAC sessions have influenced their adaptation processes.

Observation: The researcher will observe a series of LAC sessions to gain insights into the dynamics, discussions, and specific strategies shared among teachers.

Reflective Journals: The teachers will be asked to maintain reflective journals over a period of four weeks, documenting their day-to-day experiences and strategies in managing the new subject time allocation.

Document Review: The study will review LAC session materials, curriculum guides, and any personal notes or lesson plans shared by the teachers.

Data Analysis

The surveys will be statistically analyzed to establish trend and correlation of data. Qualitative interview data would then be analyzed using thematic analysis, thereby extracting common themes and insights related to the experiences and strategies involved by the teachers.

Observations in checklists help triangulate data, giving a comprehensive view of how effective the sessions of LAC are. This type of data obtained from a survey would be analyzed using statistical software to come up with descriptive statistics that would include mean scores and the frequency distribution. There could also be correlation analyses to observe what kind of relationships there are between variables. For instance, perceived effectiveness of LAC sessions could be correlated with teachers' preparedness. Qualitative data from interviews will be coded using thematic analysis to help identify the underlying themes and patterns. It is possible to grasp in-depth how teachers perceive and respond to the curriculum and time-allocation changes through this coding process.

Ethical Considerations

In adapting and coping with the MATATAG Curriculum New Subject Time Allocation for Grade 4 Teachers in GES, the researcher addressed several ethical considerations that ensures; equity and fair, transparency in decision-making, professional integrity, student-centered approach, stress and well-being of teachers, accountability and responsibility, consent and autonomy, long-term impact on educational outcome, informed consent and communication with parents, and respect for diverse learners need. By keeping these considerations in mind, educators can ensure that their actions are fair, transparent, and in the best interest of their students, while also maintaining their own professional integrity and well-being.

Results and Discussion

Cross-Case Synthesis Chart

Based on the research questionnaire, here is a table summarizing the results of the adaptation strategies used by the 4 Grade Four Teachers in GES.

Table 1. *Adaptation Strategies of Grade 4 Teachers*

<i>Adaptation Strategy</i>	<i>Teacher A</i>	<i>Teacher B</i>	<i>Teacher C</i>	<i>Teacher D</i>	<i>Commonality/Unique Aspects</i>
Reorganizing Lesson Plans	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Common (Used by 3 out of 4 teachers)
Collaborative Planning	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Common (Used by 3 out of 4 teachers)
Incorporating Multidisciplinary Approaches	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Common (Used by 3 out of 4 teachers)
Peer Support	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Common (Used by 3 out of 4 teachers)
Use of Technology	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Common (Used by 3 out of 4 teachers)

Table 1 shows the cross-case synthesis chart of the different adaptation strategies used by the four Grade 4 teachers in GES wherein Teachers A, B and D commonly approved the strategy of reorganizing the lesson plans, on the other hand Teacher C did not agree with reorganizing of lesson plans as he believed that the available evidence suggested not that technology creates educational improvement but rather that educational improvement comes about through coherent instruction and assessment that supports high-quality student learning (Goldman, Lawless, Pellegrino, & Plants, 2005–2006; Newman, Smith, Allensworth, & Bryk, 2001).

The Collaborative Planning Strategy was agreed by Teachers B, C and D while Teacher A believed that a learning environment is adaptive if it can monitor user activities, interpreted them using domain-specific models, infer user requirements, and act on available knowledge to dynamically facilitated the learning process (Paramythis, 2003).

Teachers A, C and D adapted incorporating multidisciplinary approaches, in contrary Teacher B considered that with multiple instructors there is increased flexibility in grouping and scheduling, thus making it possible for students to experience less wait time for teacher attention and increased time on task, an important factor documented to increased academic productivity (Kneedler & Hallahan, 1981; Lloyd, 1982; Wheldall & Panagopoulou-Stamatelatu, 1991).

Peer Support Strategy was commonly accepted by Teacher A, B and D this knowledge base has consistently indicated that high-quality professional development activities are longer in duration (contact hours plus follow-up), provide access to new technologies for teaching and learning, actively engaged teachers in meaningful and relevant activities for their individual contexts, promote peer collaboration and community building, and have a clearly articulated and a common vision for student achievement (Adelman et al., 2002; NFIE, 1996; Porter et al., 2000; Sparks, 2002). In contrast, Teacher C does not rely on peer support, which could suggest either independence or a different support structure in place.

The traditional methods focused and emphasized mainly on the learning of grammar rule and vocabulary and as such do not pay much attention to the four skills mainly LSRW. While writing, students are mainly dependent on grammar rules and translating them from their native tongue and while reading, “grammar translation method produced habits indicative of deciphering and not of reading” (Tyler 2008), where Teacher B supported with. On the other hand, Teachers A, C and D believed that the use of technology is more efficient than traditional ones.

In summary, 75% of the teachers used most of the strategies, which shows that using technology, changing lesson plans, working together on plans, taking multi-subject approaches, and giving peer support are common and work well for teachers that allowed them to adapt and cope-up with the MATATAG Curriculum New Subject Time Allocation. Knowing these differences inside and out can help back up teachers based on what they need and make sure they're all ready to handle the changes.

Thematic Analysis Chart

To conduct a thematic analysis, the qualitative data from interviews, observations, and journals will be categorized into themes. Below is a chart that organizes the data into common themes, patterns, and variations observed in how the teachers adapt and cope with the new curriculum requirements.

Table 2. *Adaptation and Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Common Patterns</i>	<i>Variations</i>	<i>Example Quotes/Observations</i>
Theme 1: Reorganization of Lesson Plans	How teachers modify lesson plans to fit new time allocations.	Most teachers adapt by shortening lessons or combining topics.	Some teachers struggle with reorganizing due to content depth or lack of resources.	"I had to condense the lessons to ensure we cover all topics within the allocated time."
Theme 2: Collaborative Planning	Involvement in planning with other teachers to share ideas and strategies.	Teachers frequently participate in team planning sessions, sharing materials and	A few teachers prefer to work independently due to time constraints or differing	"Collaborating with my colleagues has helped me find new ways to approach

Themes	Description	Common Patterns	Variations	Example Quotes/Observations
Theme 3: Multidisciplinary Approaches	Integration of multiple subjects to maximize teaching time and enhance learning.	Teachers commonly use interdisciplinary projects to connect different subjects.	teaching methods. Some teachers find it challenging to implement due to rigid subject boundaries or lack of experience.	the curriculum." "I combined math and science in a project, which made the learning experience more cohesive for students."
Theme 4: Peer Support	Seeking and offering support to colleagues, sharing challenges and solutions.	Peer support is a key coping mechanism, with teachers exchanging advice and emotional support.	teaching styles. Variations in the level of support sought; some rely heavily on peers, while others prefer self-reliance.	"Talking to my peers has been invaluable, especially when I feel overwhelmed."
Theme 5: Use of Technology	Leveraging digital tools to enhance teaching and manage time constraints.	Many teachers use technology to streamline lesson delivery and engage students more effectively.	Some teachers face difficulties due to lack of access to technology or insufficient training.	"Using educational apps has saved time and made lessons more interactive, but access can be an issue."
Theme 6: Emotional and Professional Stress	Emotional and professional challenges faced by teachers due to curriculum changes.	Teachers commonly report feelings of stress and pressure due to the new requirements.	Variations in stress levels; some cope well with changes, while others experience significant anxiety.	"The changes have been overwhelming at times but talking it through with colleagues has helped."
Theme 7: Professional Development Needs	The need for further training and resources to adapt to curriculum changes effectively.	Most teachers express a desire for more professional development opportunities related to the new curriculum.	Some teachers feel current training is sufficient, while others believe it is inadequate or poorly timed.	"I feel that more training on how to integrate technology into my lessons would be really beneficial."
Theme 8: Student Engagement and Outcomes	Impact of adaptation strategies on student engagement and learning outcomes.	Teachers generally observe positive student engagement when using new strategies.	Some report mixed results, particularly when struggling to manage time or integrate new approaches.	"Students are more engaged with the multidisciplinary projects, but it's a challenge to keep up with the pace."

Explanation:

Themes: Wide-ranging groups we pinpoint from the qualitative data showing key areas teachers focus on as they adapt and cope.

Description: A short rundown of what each theme covers.

Common Patterns: Things we see across many teachers pointing to shared experiences or ways of handling things.

Variations: How individual teachers differ in their experience or approach to each theme showing the range of ways they adapt.

Example Quotes/Observations: Word-for-word quotes from interviews or things we've seen that bring the theme to life giving real-world examples of how these themes play out in practice

The thematic analysis chart serves as a tool to systematically identify and organize the key themes emerging from the qualitative data. By highlighting common patterns and variations, this chart provides a clear understanding of how Grade 4 teachers in the GES are adapting and coping with the MATATAG Curriculum's new subject time allocations. This analysis can inform targeted interventions and support strategies to better assist teachers in this transition.

Adaptation Strategies

Many have purported that this deficiency can be attributed to an insufficient number of hours of professional development. In light of this, there has been a steady increase in the quantity of professional development opportunities, across all pedagogical domains, afforded to teachers over the past several years (e.g., Fishman, Best, Marx, & Tal, 2001b). However, although the number of professional development opportunities for teachers has increased, our understanding about what constitutes quality professional development, “what teachers learn from it, or its impact on student outcomes has not substantially increased “(Fishman, Best, Marx & Tal, 2001a; Wilson & Berne, 1999). We have found out that there are a lot of adaptation strategies the teacher should apply in order to adapt with the new subject time allocation by the MATATAG Curriculum these are reorganizing of lesson plans, collaborative planning, incorporating multidisciplinary approaches, peer collaboration and the use of technology. Cabrero (2006), points out how the applied teaching strategies will take effect on the teaching quality, not only from an individual point of view, but also on the collaboration of the group.

Collaborative Planning

Fladd et al. (2021) cited that most teachers adapt by shortening lessons or combining topics, Teachers frequently participate in team planning sessions, sharing materials and teaching methods, Teachers commonly use Jacob (2015) interdisciplinary projects to connect different subjects, Peer support is a key coping mechanism, with teachers exchanging advice and emotional support, Many teachers use technology to streamline lesson delivery and engage students more effectively, Teachers commonly report feelings of stress and

pressure due to the new requirements, Most teachers express a desire for more professional development opportunities related to the new curriculum, Teachers generally observe positive student engagement when using new strategies (Parsons & Taylor, 2011).

Role of LAC Sessions

The implementation of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) enhances the teaching and learning process to achieve the addressed goals in the curriculum (Culajara, 2022a). These goals address equality and quality services in education, thus this can be implemented when improving teachers' professional development through Social Learning Action Cell (SLAC) the instructional leaders and teachers have the grit in improving their competencies through professional development. To transform learning and make it worthwhile, teachers must have a thorough awareness of the value of instructional models and how they work in the instructional process. The main forces behind curriculum development are teachers who serve as instructional leaders (Arrieta, 2021). As stipulated by the Department of Education Republic of the Philippines (2016), Learning Action Cell goals include enhancing teachers' competencies in contextualizing instructional delivery and integrating the principles of global citizenship education into instruction. The Learning Action Cell is a K–12 Education Program school-based continuing professional development strategy. This is strengthened by the study of Binauhan (2019) Learning Action Cell (LAC), teachers work together to enhance their professional development and empower members to act as changemakers. In order to adapt to the quick changes, the teaching profession needs a continuous improvement mindset (Silva, 2021). With the Learning Action Cell, the achievement is more integrated with the vision and mission of the organization to be future-ready and ready for every change in our educational system (Javier, 2021). Furthermore, as Culajara et al. (2022) stated that teachers must understand how to interact with students and provide effective and efficient instruction.

Conclusions

The research on Grade 4 teachers' adaptation and coping strategies in relation to the MATATAG Curriculum reveals the enormous understanding of the problems and opportunities that this new subject time distribution poses. The findings are an indication of preparedness by teachers on the general level, but with pertinent gaps that need professional targeted direction and support.

The LAC sessions will facilitate collaboration among educators to collectively confront challenges, share effective practices, and reflect on their experiences. These enhance teachers' instructional capabilities and impact positively on student engagement and learning outcomes.

But since continuous training and resources cannot substitute the support systems that actually empower teachers to proficiently handle the issues of the MATATAG Curriculum, one hopes through LAC sessions developing a collaboration and professional growth culture that education stakeholders will finally make their contributions toward having improved quality Grade 4 student education in the Philippines.

The three most common strategies among the teachers included lesson plan reorganization, collaborative planning as well as peer support, with 75% of the teachers applying each of these. This indicates that there is a focus on these areas by teachers in adjusting to new time allocations. Regarding different strategies that each teacher has, there exists a unique combination of approaches for every teacher, hence no solitary approach to coping with curriculum changes. The use of differing strategies illustrates the need for flexibility in the support systems for GES teachers to enable them to use approaches that suit their pedagogy or circumstances. For most of the teachers, technology and a multidisciplinary approach is important in that it emphasizes celebration of innovative approaches in the current education environment. However, some teachers will need extended support to make it happen in practice.

Strengthen Collaborative Planning: Given its importance, collaborative planning sessions should be encouraged and supported, possibly integrating more technology and multidisciplinary approaches within these sessions.

Provide Technology Training: Since technology is a vital tool, GES could offer additional training to ensure all teachers can effectively integrate technology into their teaching.

Share Best Practices: Teachers like Teacher D, who use all strategies, could share their approaches in LAC sessions to help other teachers who might not be utilizing all available strategies.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ruth C. Colon

Gabi Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines